

Influence of Soapnut on Capillarity Control

D. N. PATHAK and G. N. PANT

Department of Chemistry, Regional Institute of Technology, Jamshedpur

Manuscript received 18 September 1973; revised 13 March 1975; accepted 29 April 1975

Seepage loss through earthen embankments and levees and canals often makes surrounding agricultural land unfit for further cultivation because of salinity intrusions. Of the various methods of controlling seepage, action of surface active agents on soils has been found to be most effective. Laboratory experiments with standard sands saturated with different percentages of cheaply available and economically feasible commercial saponin compound namely, soapnut (*Sapindus mukorossi*) show that 0.3% concentration of the mixture gives the best result and that beyond this concentration the capillary rise, which accounts seepage, is again in the increasing order. Preferential adsorption of colloidal particles on the solid surfaces of the soil explains this characteristic property of saponin compound.

It is well known that capillarity is responsible for storage of water in soils, which accounts for the movement of water from moist region to drier regions and according to Buckingham¹ is comparable to the flow of heat through a wire. For the flow of water through a column of soils under saturated conditions Darcy² enunciated a law, which later on was modified by Richard¹⁰ and Child & Collis George² to make it applicable under unsaturated conditions.

In the past many experimenters^{4-6,8,11} tried to check the capillarity in soils by use of chemicals. The present investigation attempts to find out the percentage of a popular saponin compound, Sapindus Mukorissi (Triterpene Saponin : Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C.S.I.R., 1956) commercially known as Ritha (soapnut) required to be added in the soil for checking capillary rise.

Experimental

Standard Ennore sands of 3 grades, passing through and retained on respectively B.S. (25-50), B.S. (50-100) and B.S. (-100) were used as the soil media. The pericarp of dry soapnut was powdered and sieved through a 100 B.S. sieve. This powder was mixed with each of the three sands, so as to make 0%, 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, 0.4% and 0.5% mixtures of powder concentrations. Sand soapnut mixtures were prepared by initially weighing a known quantity of sand and the desired percentage of powder by weight and mixing them thoroughly with an amount of distilled water equivalent to the saturated moisture content of sand. Due to the hydrophobic nature of the soapnut, rejection of water was observed. The treated sands were thoroughly mixed and dried first in air and then in oven maintained at 45°. This temperature was chosen to test the sample in conditions prevailing in the hottest month of the year.

Capillary rise experiments were carried in a 45 cm long perspex cylinder of 7 cm diameter, with openings at every 2 cm intervals, one end of which being kept open and the other fitted with a perspex perforated

disc attached with a B.S. 150 mesh sieve by chloroform, to ensure retention of sands but to give free access to water movement. At first the openings of the cylinder were closed with plastic clay and then filled with the sample. To have uniformity of filling the length of the cylinder was divided into five equal parts and after filling each part the cylinder was tapped gently for 5 times. The cylinder was then vertically placed in an enamelled trough and water was poured in it upto about 2 mm below the first opening in the cylinder. This depth of water was maintained during the experiment by pouring more water when necessary. The rise of water in the sand-soapnut mixtures were noted. The moisture content at various levels was determined by subtracting dry weight from the wet weight of the sample. To determine wet weight moist samples were taken with the help of glass tubes after removing plastic clay at various openings in a number of weighed cans.

Surface tension of 0.1%, 0.15%, 0.2%, 0.25%, 0.3%, 0.35%, 0.4%, 0.45% and 0.5% soap solutions were determined using a Stalagmometer.

Discussion

The experimental results (Table 1) clearly show that the height of capillary rise decreases with the increase in soapnut concentration only upto 0.3% and beyond this concentration the capillary rise again increases which indicates that any further increase in powder concentrations gives no added advantage in reducing the height of capillary rise. The distribution of moisture is also affected upto 0.3% only. The bottom layers, namely near the saturated front accumulate more moisture and the percentage of moisture towards the top becomes less as 0.3% concentration is approached. Further increase of soapnut concentration to 0.4% and 0.5% vitiates both the results of capillary rise and moisture distribution. As seepage loss is proportional to moisture gradient or the potential gradient existing

TABLE I—CAPILLARY RISE CHARACTERISTICS IN SAND

Percentage of soapnut by weight	B.S. (25-50)		B.S. (50-100)		B.S. (-100)	
	Height of probing (cm)	Moisture content (g)	Height of probing (cm)	Moisture content (g)	Height of probing (cm)	Moisture content (g)
0.0	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.2640	2.00	0.2810
	2.00	0.2470	4.00	0.2500	6.00	0.2780
	4.00	0.1818	6.00	0.2520	10.00	0.2530
	6.00	0.1270	8.00	0.1850	14.00	0.1830
	8.25	0	10.00	0.1340	18.00	0.0820
			15.50	0	22.50	0
0.1	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.2880	2.00	0.3080
	2.00	0.2870	4.00	0.2550	4.00	0.2920
	4.00	0.1365	6.00	0.2140	6.00	0.2170
	6.00	0	8.00	0.1140	10.00	0.1850
			12.50	0	14.00	0.0750
				18.15	0	
0.2	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.2960	2.00	0.3060
	2.00	0.3250	4.00	0.2430	6.00	0.2960
	4.00	0.1990	6.00	0.1920	10.00	0.2050
	5.50	0	8.00	0.1650	14.00	0.1530
			10.00	0	18.00	0.0960
				18.85	0	
0.3	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.3050	2.00	0.3060
	2.00	0.3250	4.00	0.1830	6.00	0.2960
	4.00	0.1660	6.00	0.1210	10.00	0.2050
	5.10	0	8.00	0	14.00	0.1530
			8.70	0	18.00	0.0960
				18.85	0	
0.4	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.2560	2.00	0.2870
	2.00	0.2800	4.00	0.2300	4.00	0.2450
	4.00	0.1970	6.00	0.1670	10.00	0.1870
	5.30	0	8.00	0.1200	14.00	0.1350
			10.00	0.0685	18.00	0.0860
		12.20	0	19.25	0	
0.5	Saturated level		Saturated level	0.3140	Saturated level	0.3200
		0.3300	2.00	0.2540	2.00	0.2730
	2.00	0.2560	4.00	0.2320	6.00	0.2650
	4.00	0.1160	6.00	0.1720	10.00	0.2500
	5.80	0	8.00	0.1250	14.00	0.1680
			10.00	0.0760	18.00	0.0630
		12.40	0	20.45	0	

between the surfaces, it can be deduced from our experimental results that seepage will be least for the 0.3% concentration mixture in all the three grades of sands.

The nature of distribution of moisture in the capillary rise is governed by the effectiveness of the chemical agent added. Stronger the action of the surface active agent more will be the pull of moisture content down towards the bottom. For the in filtra-

tion of organic liquids in soils Mustafa *et al*⁷ used the following equation :

$$D = Di[(r/\eta)\cos H]$$

where D = diffusivity of a liquid, r = liquid air surface tension, η = liquid viscosity, H = liquid solid contact angle, Di = intrinsic diffusivity. But this equation has its limitations and according to Philip⁸

is applicable only to sufficiently dry soils and becomes progressively less accurate as the liquid content increases. Soapnut is a surface active organic agent which forms colloidal solutions with low surface tensions, when comes in contact with water. The results indicate that surface tension of colloidal solutions of soapnut decreases appreciably upto 0.3% and again begins to rise beyond this concentration (Figure 1).

of hydration and nature of displacing ions. Upto a minimum stability limit, the long chain ions of soapnut are adsorbed due to electrostatic force with their head groups pointing towards the surface and their carbon chains floating in the bulk making the surface hydrophobic. This hydrophobic condition is maximum at minimum stability, because of the adsorption of a thin or a compact monolayer

Variation of surface tension of Soapnut with concentration.

Fig. 1

This may be one of the reasons for inhibition of capillary rise only upto 0.3% concentration.

Preferential adsorption of colloidal particles of soapnut on solid surfaces of soil further explains our results. Chemically soils are aluminosilicate systems and characterised by possessing exposed surface layers rich in oxygen atoms and hydroxyl group. These surfaces are highly polar and possess an intense residual force. When soil comes in contact with water, the system being electrically neutral, such ions as those of H^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{++} , Ca^{++} and the like when present are adsorbed from the aqueous soil solution to counterbalance the surface charge, thereby forming an electrical double layer. In the absence of other ions, water molecules themselves play the role of cations to balance this charge. The ions forming the outer layer can be exchanged or displaced by other ions according to the extent

depending upon the anchorage of the polar group. As the concentration of the surfactant is increased beyond the minimum, due to a strong attraction of the Vander Waals type⁸ a second layer is adsorbed with the polar group pointing away from the surface, thereby imparting hydrophilic nature to it and consequently it leads to dispersion. Thus upto a certain concentration soapnut makes the soil hydrophobic which leads to check the capillary rise of water and beyond this concentration it makes the soil hydrophilic resulting in the increase of capillary rise.

Soapnut is abundantly available in India and each kilogramme of it in the natural form yields about 400 g of powder passing through B.S. 100 sieve and costs about Rs. 3.00. Our investigation revealed that this compound may be economically utilized to effectively control the seepage losses in earth dams.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. V. K. Sarma, Assistant Professor, Applied Mechanics Department, Regional Institute of Technology, Jamshedpur for his keen interest and help in this research work.

References

1. E. BUCKINGHAM, *U.S. Dept. Agr. Bur. Soils Bull.*, 1907, 38.
2. E. C. CHILD and N. C. COLLIS GEORGE, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, A201, 392.
3. H. DARCY, "Les Fontaines Publiques de la ville de Dijon", 1856 (The public water supply of the city of Dijon, Dalmont, Paris 1856).
4. B. L. DHAWAN, Ph.D. Thesis submitted to Lucknow University 1967.
5. W. GARDENER and J. A. WIDTSON, *Soil Sci.*, 1921, 11, 215.
6. O. G. INGLES, *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1968, 18, 291
7. M. A. MUSTAFA, J. LETEY and C. L. WATSON, *Soil Sci Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1970, 34, 369.
8. R. H. OTTEWILL, M. C. RASTOGI and A. WATANABE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 56, 854.
9. J. R. PHILIP, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1971, 35, 607.
10. L. A. RICHARDS, *Physics*, 1931, 1, 318.
11. D. R. WILLONGEBY, K. A. GROSS, O. G. INGLES, S. R. SILVA and V. M. SPIERS, Proc. of the 4th Conf. of the Australian Road Research Board, 1968, Vol. 4, part 2, p. 1386.